

Synthesis of a few Sulfonylhydrazides, Acid Hydrazides, and their Derivatives and 1',2,4'-triazoles from 1-Phenyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole

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3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazole-4'-sulfonyl hydrazide, 3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-*p*-sulfonamido-4'-benzoyl hydrazide, 3,5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-*p*-sulfonamido-3'-benzoyl hydrazide were obtained from 3,5-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole and their N-benzylidene derivatives were prepared. 4'-Arylsubstituted-5'-mercapto-1',2',4'-triazolyl-3-*p*'-phenylsulfonamido-*p*-1-phenyl-3, 5-dimethyl pyrazoles and 4'-arylsubstituted-5'-mercapto-1', 2',4'-triazolyl-3-*m*'-phenyl sulfonamido-*p*-1-phenyl-3,5 dimethyl pyrazoles were prepared from acid hydrazides. All the hydrazides and their N-benzylidene derivatives were screened for antibacterial activity.

IN view of encouraging results obtained during the course of earlier work on the synthesis and antibacterial screening of few hydrazides and their derivatives^{1,2} and the synthesis of 1, 2, 4-triazoles³, it was thought of interest to extend such work on heterocyclic compounds and study their antibacterial and pharmacological properties.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of sulfonyl hydrazides (III), acid hydrazides (VI) containing sulfonamide moiety attached to 3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole and their N-benzylidene derivatives. The hydrazides (VI) were then condensed with few isothiocyanates to yield (VIII) which on cyclisation gave 4'-aryl substituted-5'-mercapto-1', 2', 4'-triazolyl-3-*p*' (and 3-*m*')-phenyl sulfonamido-*p*-1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl pyrazoles (IX). All the hydrazides and their N-benzylidene derivatives have been screened for their antibacterial activity.

Scheme - A

- I, R=H
II, R=-SO₂Cl
III, R=-SO₂NHNH₂
IV, R=-SO₂NHN=CHAr

Scheme—B

- V, R = -SO₂NHC₆H₄COOH (*p*-; *m*-)
VI, R = -SO₂NHC₆H₄CONHNH₂ (" ")
VII, R = -SO₂NHC₆H₄CONHN=CHAr (" ")
VIII, R = -SO₂NHC₆H₄CONHNHCNHA_r (" ")

(similarly with *m*-aminobenzoic acid)

Experimental :

3,5-Dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazole required was prepared by the method reported in the literature⁴. Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

3,5-Dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazole-4'-sulfonyl chloride(II)

0.1 mole of 3,5-dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazole(I) was taken in (50 ml) chloroform and (0.6 moles) chlorosulfonic acid was added dropwise with stirring at 5°-10°. The mixture was then refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 6 hr, cooled and poured into crushed ice. The entire solution was extracted with chloroform, and the chloroform extract rinsed thoroughly with cold water, and

evaporated to yield the corresponding sulfonyl chloride(II). Purified by crystallisation from Petroleum ether (40°-60°). M.P. 40°-41°, yield 60%.

The chlorosulfonation was also carried out at room temperature using chloroform solvent and (0.3 moles) chlorosulfonic acid to (0.1 mole) of (I), for 24 hr. At the end of which the mixture was poured into crushed ice. 3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-pyrazole-4'-sulfonic acid precipitated out was filtered and crystallised from hot water. One part of sulfonic acid was heated with $1\frac{1}{2}$ parts of PCl_5 for 1 hr. Excess of PCl_5 was decomposed by the addition of cold water and extracted with chloroform as above, gave the sulfonyl chloride II.

3, 5-Dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-4'-sulfonyl hydrazide (III) :

Sulfonyl chloride (II) (0.05 mole) was dissolved in 50 ml dry absolute ethanol and cooled to 0°. To this cold solution (0.1 mole) was added 98-100% hydrazine hydrate slowly with shaking. During the addition of hydrazine, the temperature was maintained at 0°-5°, after which the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at 0°-5°. The precipitated compound was filtered and the filtrate on diluting with cold water yielded a further crop, separated by filtration. The residue obtained in both cases was washed repeatedly with cold water and crystallised from ethanol. M.P. 137°, yield 71%. (Found. C, 49.57, H 4.08, N 21.1, S 11.94, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{S}$ Requires : C. 49.63, H 4.13, N 21.05, S 12.03%).

N-Benzylidene-3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-4'-sulfonyl hydrazide (IV).....Table 1.

Equimolar amounts of hydrazide (III) and appropriate aromatic aldehydes were refluxed with ethanol for 1 hr. The product separated on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 58-70%.

3,5-Dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-4'-benzoic acid (V *p*-) :

Sulfonyl chloride (II) (0.1 mole) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (0.1 mole) were heated under reflux for 2 hr. using pyridine (70 ml) as a base. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into dilute hydrochloric acid (2*N*). The precipitated compound was filtered and washed with water till the washings are neutral and recrystallised from ethanol. M.P. 208°-10° ; yield 61%. (Found : C 58.16 ; H 4.53 ; N 11.27 ; S 8.56 ; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ Requires ; C 58.22 ; H 4.58 ; N 11.32 ; S 8.62%).

3, 5-Dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-4'-benzoyl hydrazide (VI *p*-) :

Compound (V *p*-) was esterified and the ester was then treated with 95% hydrazine hydrate^{1,2} to furnish (VI *p*-) M.P. 249°-50°, yield 79% (Found : C 56.03 ; H 4.87 ; N 18.12 ; S 8.24 ; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}$ Requires : C 56.10 ; H 4.93 ; N 18.18 ; S 8.31%).

N-Benzylidene-3, 5-dimethyl pyrazole-1-phenyl-*p*-sulfonamido-4'-benzoyl hydrazide (VIII *p*-) were prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of (VI-*p*-)₁ with appropriate aldehydes as above. Yield 55-69%. The results are depicted in Table 2.

Similarly, 3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-3'-benzoic acid (V *m*-) was prepared by condensing the sulfonyl chloride (II) with *m*-aminobenzoic acid m.p. 162°, yield 57%. 3, 5-Dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-3'-benzoyl hydrazide (VI *m*-) m.p. 181°, yield 74% and *N*-benzylidene-3, 5-dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-3'-benzoyl hydrazide (VII *m*-) yield 52-70%, (Table 3) were prepared by the above method.

3',5'-Dimethyl-1'-phenylpyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-*p*'-benzoyl-4-aryl substituted thiosemicarbazide (VIII) Table 4.

An equimolar quantities of (VI *p*-) and different aryl isothiocyanates was refluxed in ethanol for 3 hr. On cooling the solid product separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 58-71%.

Similarly 3',5'-dimethyl-1'-phenylpyrazole-*p*-sulfonamido-*m*'-benzoyl-4-aryl substituted thiosemicarbazides (VIII *m*-) were prepared and their results are entered in Table 5. Yield 56-73%.

4'-Aryl substituted-5'-mercapto-1',2',4'-triazolyl-3'-*p*'-phenyl sulfonamido-*p*-1-phenyl-3, 5-dimethylpyrazole (IX *p*-) Table 6.

0.01 mole of thiosemicarbazide (VIII *p*-), 2*N* sodium hydroxide (20 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid till just acidic. The product separating was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. This procedure was followed to prepare other 1',2',4'-triazolyl pyrazoles, yield 60-70%.

Similar procedure was adopted to obtain 4'-aryl substituted-5'-mercapto-1', 2', 4'-triazolyl-3'-*m*'-phenyl sulfonamido-*p*-1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl pyrazole (IX *m*-). The results are entered in Table 7. Yield 58-69%.

TABLE 1—*N*-BENZYLIDENE-3,5-DIMETHYL-1-PHENYLPYRAZOLE-4'-SULFONYL HYDRAZIDES (IV)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				N		S	
			Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	
1.	C_6H_5	147	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{S}$	15.82	15.7	9.04	8.92
2.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	169	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$	15.14	15.04	8.64	8.56
3.	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	155	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$	14.58	14.46	8.33	8.25
4.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	190	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_5\text{S}$	17.54	17.63	8.01	7.89
5.	2-Furyl	141	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{S}$	16.28	16.12	9.30	9.21

TABLE 2—N-BENZYLIDENE-3,5-DIMETHYL-1-PHENYLPYRAZOLE-*p*-SULFONAMIDO-4'-BENZOYLHYDRAZIDE (VII)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				Calc.	N Found	Calc.	S Found
6.	C ₆ H ₅	261	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	14.80	14.71	6.76	6.65
7.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	230	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₅ S	14.32	14.32	6.54	6.46
8.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	239	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	13.92	13.81	6.21	6.13
9.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	248	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₅ S	16.22	16.09	6.17	6.06
10.	2-Furyl	228	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S	14.53	14.46	6.91	6.82

TABLE 3—N-BENZYLIDENE-3,5-DIMETHYL-1-PHENYLPYRAZOLE-*p*-SULFONAMIDO-3'-BENZOYL HYDRAZIDE (VII)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				Calc.	N Found	Calc.	S Found
11.	C ₆ H ₅	220	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	14.80	14.69	6.76	6.69
12.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	215	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₅ S	14.32	14.27	6.54	6.42
13.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	233	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	13.92	13.84	6.21	6.09
14.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	187	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₅ S	16.22	16.04	6.17	6.10
15.	2-Furyl	201	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S	14.53	14.41	6.91	6.78

TABLE 4—3'-5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PHENYLPYRAZOLYL-*p*-SULFONAMIDO-*p'*-BENZOYL-4-ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (VIII *p*-)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				Calc.	N Found	Calc.	S Found
16.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	161	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	15.73	15.68	11.99	11.89
17.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	179	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂ Cl	15.15	15.07	11.54	11.42
18.	1-Naphthyl	200	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	14.73	14.66	11.23	11.18

TABLE 5—3'-5'-DIMETHYL-1'-PHENYLPYRAZOLYL-*p*-SULFONAMIDO-*m'*-BENZOYL-4-ARYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDE (VIII *m*-)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				Calc.	N Found	Calc.	S Found
19.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	194	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	15.73	15.62	11.99	11.92
20.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	206	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂ Cl	15.15	15.10	11.54	11.42
21.	1-Naphthyl	185	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	14.73	14.66	11.23	11.15

TABLE 6—4'-ARYL-5'-MERCAPTO-1',2',4'-TRIAZOLYL-3'-*p'*-PHENYLSULFONAMIDO-*p*-1-PHENYL-3,5-DIMETHYL PYRAZOLE (IX)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				Calc.	N Found	Calc.	S Found
22.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	145	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	16.29	16.14	12.41	12.32
23.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	158	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂ Cl	15.66	15.55	11.93	11.79
24.	1-Naphthyl	170	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	15.22	15.05	11.60	11.47

TABLE 7—4'-ARYL-5'-MERCAPTO-1',2',4'-TRIAZOLYL-3'-*m'*-PHENYL SULFONAMIDO-*p*-1-PHENYL-3,5-DIMETHYL PYRAZOLE (IX)

Nos.	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis %			
				Calc.	N Found	Calc.	S Found
25.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	182	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	16.29	16.18	12.41	12.29
26.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	199	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂ Cl	15.66	15.59	11.93	11.86
27.	1-Naphthyl	155	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	15.22	15.14	11.60	11.41

Screening for antibacterial activity

Compounds III, IV (p-; m-) and those listed in tables 1, 2, 3 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were as follows: *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella flexneri*. The antibacterial activity was tested by ditch-plate technique⁵, using the concentration levels of 1 mg and 3 mg per ml.

Compd. III inhibited the growth of *S. typhi*, and *Shi. flexneri* at the concentration levels of 3 mg/ml. Compd. VI (m-) inhibited the growth of *Stap. aureus* at the concentration of 3 mg/ml. Compd. 2, Table 1 inhibited completely the growth of *B. subtilis* and *Staph. aureus* at the concentration levels of 1 mg and 3 mg/ml. Compd. No. 7, Table 2 only inhibited *Stap. aureus* at the concentration of 1 mg and 3 mg per ml. The compound (VI p-) and remaining compounds listed in Tables 1, 2, 3 were found to be completely ineffective against all the organisms employed.

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